

Passive Load-Follow Operation of Small Long-life Molten Salt Fast Reactor with Moderating Reflector

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the feasibility of passive load-follow operation (PLFO) in a small molten salt fast reactor (MSFR) employing a moderating reflector. The concept preserves key advantages of the MSFR by introducing localized moderation in a reflector-based flux-trapped configuration, thereby reducing the required fuel inventory for long-life operation without refueling. However, moderating reflectors such as BeO and MgO exhibit a positive reflector temperature coefficient (RTC), induced by the flux-trapped configuration, which introduces a rather delayed feedback behavior distinct from conventional fuel temperature feedback. To assess the impact of positive reflector temperature feedback on transient behavior, a circulating-fuel kinetics model, a simplified thermal-hydraulic (TH) model of the primary circuit, and a heat conduction model of the reflector region were integrated. PLFO was simulated under transient scenarios, as this strategy is expected to be well suited for MSFRs due to their strongly negative fuel temperature coefficient. A distinguishing feature of this work is the explicit treatment of neutron-gamma heating in the reflector region as a function of time-dependent fission power, along with region-wise reflector temperature feedback. The analyses evaluate the evolution of fission power, the power transferred to the secondary system, and the fuel and reflector temperature profiles, while quantifying their respective reactivity feedback contributions. The results demonstrate that proper implementation of reflector temperature feedback is essential for reliable transient prediction.

Keywords: Molten salt fast reactor, Chloride salt, Moderating reflector, Positive reflector temperature feedback, Neutron-gamma heating

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten salt reactors (MSRs) offer distinctive features due to their use of liquid fuel salts, including enhanced inherent safety and sustainability, which are particularly attractive for small modular reactors (SMRs) applications such as maritime systems. As a strategy for a 30-year long-life MSR, an MSFR concept incorporating a moderating reflector has been proposed, providing design simplicity and a reduced fuel inventory compared with conventional purely fast-spectrum MSFRs. This design avoids strict online fuel management with the fast-spectrum in the active core and eliminates in-core structural components with limited lifetimes. However, this configuration exhibits a unique behavior in the form of a positive reflector temperature coefficient (RTC) [1]. Although the isothermal temperature coefficient (ITC) remains sufficiently negative due to a strong negative fuel temperature coefficient (FTC), the positive feedback from the reflector can challenge simple passive load-follow operation (PLFO), particularly when coupled with neutron-gamma heating.

2. REACTOR CHARACTERISTICS & TRANSIENT ANALYSES METHOD

2.1. Reactor Concept of Maritime MSFR

Figure 1 shows the design configuration of the reference maritime MSFR, which utilizes a NaCl-KCl-UCl₃ chloride fuel salt and is surrounded by a BeO moderating reflector. An inner barrier, consisting of 8 mm SS316 and a 0.8 mm Inconel 625 cladding, is located at the interface between the BeO reflector and the fuel salt region. Through localized moderation in the BeO region, the design achieves 27

effective full-power years of operation at 100 MWth and a burnup of 60 MWd/kgU at the end of life, while maintaining a reduced fuel inventory. In addition, the localized moderation effect enables the use of B₄C burnable absorbers (BAs), which passively maintain excess reactivity below one dollar throughout the lifetime, while fast fission dominates the fission reactions in the active core.

Despite these advantages, the flux-trapped configurations with a moderating reflector result in a positive RTC. The mechanism can be summarized as follows: As the reflector temperature increases, the incoherent inelastic scattering cross sections increase in the thermal energy range due to enhanced thermal motion of the reflector nuclei. The local neutron spectrum near the thermal energy peak hardens, and thermal neutron absorption in the reflector region—particularly in the inner barrier—decreases. This increases the inflow of thermal neutrons into the active core, resulting in positive reactivity insertion. The overall mechanism is schematically illustrated in Figure 2. This effect is most pronounced in reflector regions adjacent to the active core, leading to region-dependent reflector temperature feedback [1].

Figure 1. Design configuration of reference maritime MSFR [1] and its simplified model for transient analyses.

Figure 2. A schematic of the positive reflector temperature coefficient (RTC) mechanism.

2.2. Reactor Characteristics & Kinetics Parameters of Simplified Analysis Model

The simplified reactor model used for transient analysis is illustrated in the right-hand side of Figure 1. The model omits components such as the control drum and B₄C shield and consists only of a 1 cm SS316 inner barrier, an outer vessel, and a 50 cm BeO reflector. The simplified configuration preserves reactor characteristics such as excess reactivity and temperature coefficients comparable to the reference design. The same BA configuration as the reference model was applied, allowing evaluation of kinetics parameters and temperature coefficients under practical operating conditions near criticality.

Table I summarizes region-wise reflector temperature coefficients at the beginning of life (BOL), obtained by perturbing only the BeO temperature. Although the nominal operating temperature is 900 K under isothermal conditions, neutron-gamma heating in the reflector region without active cooling system results in steady-state temperatures several hundred degrees higher. Therefore, coefficients in the 1200–1300 K range were consistently used, and region-wise feedback was explicitly considered. All analyses were performed under BOL (0 EFPY) conditions.

Table I. Reflector region-wise temperature coefficient at the beginning-of-life.

RTC (pcm/K)	800 – 900 K	900 – 1000 K	1000 – 1100 K	1100 – 1200 K	1200 – 1300 K
Total region	3.16 ± 0.08	2.74 ± 0.08	2.67 ± 0.08	2.12 ± 0.08	1.96 ± 0.08
Inner region (α_{R1})	2.60 ± 0.08	2.30 ± 0.08	2.05 ± 0.08	1.72 ± 0.08	1.56 ± 0.08
Mid region (α_{R2})	0.42 ± 0.08	0.41 ± 0.08	0.33 ± 0.08	0.25 ± 0.08	0.27 ± 0.08
Outer region (α_{R3})	0.10 ± 0.08	0.14 ± 0.08	0.15 ± 0.08	-0.10 ± 0.08	0.09 ± 0.08

Table II lists nominal BOL design parameters, where the inactive salt volume was assumed to be 6.5 m³ based on KAERI's analyses. Active core residence and recirculation times were evaluated assuming ideal fuel flow and fixed fuel salt flow rates, which were maintained throughout the transient analyses. The reactor was initialized in steady-state conditions consistent with these parameters.

Table III presents the kinetic parameters of the reactor model shown in Figure 1. The adjoint-weighted effective delayed neutron fractions (β_{eff}), decay constants, and prompt neutron generation time were evaluated and used in the circulating-fuel kinetics model.

Table II. Nominal design parameters at the beginning-of-life.

Thermal power (MWth)	100	Nominal core outlet temperature T_f^{out} (K)	923.7
Fuel salt mass (active core) M_c (kg)	10,667	Active core average temperature T_f^{avg} (K)	883.15
Fuel salt mass (inactive salt) M_e (kg)	21,554	Secondary salt temperature T_{IC} (K)	783.15
Fuel salt mass (heat exchanger) M_{HX} (kg)	17,214	Active core residence time τ_c (s)	4.917
Specific heat of fuel salt C_p (J·kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	568	Recirculation time τ_e (s)	9.934
Primary loop salt flow rate W (kg·s ⁻¹)	2170	Fuel Temperature coefficient α_f (pcm·K ⁻¹)	-9.41
Nominal core inlet temperature T_f^{in} (K)	842.6	Reflector temperature coefficient α_R (pcm·K ⁻¹)	1.96

Table III. Kinetic parameters of the reactor at the beginning-of-life.

Group	β_{eff} with stationary fuel salt (pcm)	β_{eff} with flowing fuel salt (pcm)	Decay constant λ_i (s ⁻¹)	Prompt neutron generation time Λ (s)
1	22.02	7.61	1.336E-02	1.1835E-04
2	117.76	43.19	3.254E-02	
3	116.03	53.35	1.212E-01	
4	273.60	167.75	3.071E-01	
5	125.72	101.82	8.663E-01	
6	52.43	49.00	2.910E+00	
Total	707.56	422.73	5.139E-01	

2.3. Transient Analyses method with Reflector Temperature Feedback

Figure 3 shows the coupled transient analysis framework, integrating neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and reflector-region heat conduction.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of Kinetics, TH and heat conduction-coupled transient analysis method.

2.3.1. Reactor kinetics and lumped primary-circuit TH model

A modified point kinetics equation (PKE) was used for time-dependent neutronic analysis, as shown in Eqs. (1) and (2). Delayed neutron losses associated with drifting precursors in the circulating fuel are included. The third and fourth terms of Eq. (2) represent precursor losses due to transport from the active core and decay in the inactive salt, respectively [2]. Applying steady-state conditions yields the flow-corrected β_{eff} shown in Table III, with a total loss of 285 pcm reflected in Eq. (1). A time step of $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s was used with an implicit Euler scheme.

$$\frac{dP(t)}{dt} = \frac{\rho(t) - \beta}{\Lambda} P(t) + \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i C_i(t) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dC_i(t)}{dt} = \frac{\beta_i}{\Lambda} P(t) - \lambda_i C_i(t) - \frac{C_i(t)}{\tau_c(t)} + \frac{C_i(t - \tau_e) \exp(-\lambda_i \tau_e)}{\tau_c(t)} \quad \text{for } i = 1 \dots 6 \quad (2)$$

The primary-circuit TH model is described by Eqs. (3)–(5) with a same time step as kinetics model. Heat transport in the active core was simplified to a single-node model with inlet and outlet temperatures and a unity power fraction. Core outlet and inlet temperatures are connected to the heat exchanger with a 1.0 s time delay, as shown in Eq. (4). Eq. (5) represents a lumped heat exchanger model assuming constant secondary salt temperature (T_{IC}), where the second term of the RHS represents the actual transferred power to the secondary circuit. The heat transfer coefficient (h_{ic}), area (A_{ic}), and secondary flow rate (Γ) were grouped into a single parameter.

$$\frac{dT_f^i(t)}{dt} = \frac{f^i}{M^i C_p} P(t) + \frac{W(t)}{M^i} (T_f^{i-1}(t) - T_f^i(t)) \quad (3)$$

$$T_{\text{HX}}^{\text{in}}(t) = T_f^{\text{out}}(t - \tau_{\text{dh}}), \quad T_f^{\text{in}}(t) = T_{\text{HX}}^{\text{out}}(t - \tau_{\text{dc}}) \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dT_{\text{HX}}^{\text{Pr}}(t)}{dt} = \frac{W(t)}{M_{\text{HX}}} (T_{\text{HX}}^{\text{in}}(t) - T_{\text{HX}}^{\text{out}}(t)) + \frac{h_{\text{ic}} A_{\text{ic}} \Gamma}{M_{\text{HX}} C_p} (T_{\text{IC}} - T_{\text{HX}}^{\text{Pr}}(t)), \quad T_{\text{HX}}^{\text{Pr}}(t) = \frac{T_{\text{HX}}^{\text{in}}(t) + T_{\text{HX}}^{\text{out}}(t)}{2} \quad (5)$$

2.3.2. Reflector heat conduction and reactivity feedback

To simulate temperature evolution in the reflector region—including the 1 cm SS316 barrier, outer vessel, and 50 cm BeO reflector—a one-dimensional transient radial heat conduction model was applied using Eq. (6), simplifying to an annular cylinder that only has a radial element. The inner and outer radii were set to 80 cm and 132 cm, respectively, with an effective height of 3.24 m to preserve reflector volume. Furthermore, heat deposition by neutron-gamma heating in the reflector was evaluated as 3.23 MWth (3.23% of total power) using iMC [3] and the spatial distribution was modeled as a 1-cm-resolved

volumetric heat source, $q_v(r)$. This source was assumed to vary in proportion to the transient fission power during the PLFO scenarios. The remaining 96.77 MWth was deposited in the fuel salt region.

Thermophysical properties of BeO and SS316, which include thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity and density, were assumed to be constant at 900 K during the PLFO [4, 5]. Convective boundary conditions were applied at SS316–fuel salt interfaces with a heat transfer coefficient of 600 W/m²·K based on KAERI CFD analyses. The finite volume method with a backward time scheme and the same 5·10⁻⁴ s time step was used. The core energy balance equation was modified accordingly to include heat exchange with SS316 surfaces as given in Eq. (7).

Temperature feedback reactivities from the reflector and fuel were calculated using Eqs. (8) and (9), based on deviations from nominal conditions. Reflector feedback was computed on a region-wise basis using volume-weighted average temperatures. The excess reactivity ρ_0 compensates for the 285 pcm delayed neutron loss.

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \cdot k \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + q_v(r, t) = \rho \cdot C_p \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dT_f^{out}(t)}{dt} = \frac{P(t)}{M_C C_p} + \frac{W(t)}{M_C} (T_f^{in}(t) - T_f^{out}(t)) + \frac{hA_S^{out}}{M_C C_p} (T_S^{out} - T_f^{in}) + \frac{hA_S^{in}}{M_C C_p} (T_S^{in} - T_f^{avg}) \quad (7)$$

$$\rho_{reflector}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha_{Ri} (T_{Ri}^{avg}(t) - T_{Ri}^{nominal}), \quad \rho_f(t) = \alpha_f (T_f^{avg}(t) - T_f^{nominal}) \quad (8)$$

$$\rho(t) = \rho_f(t) + \rho_{reflector}(t) + \rho_0 \quad (9)$$

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

PLFO was implemented by adjusting only the secondary salt flow rate to match the power demand, without any direct intervention in the fuel circuit or reactivity control system. The resulting changes in the average fuel temperature drive reactor power to balance the heat sink through negative FTC feedback. Table IV summarizes the secondary flow variations used in the PLFO scenarios, representing relatively rapid load-following conditions. In the present study, only reductions in the secondary flow rate were considered in the PLFO scenarios. However, other mechanisms—such as primary-loop flow coast-down or heat exchanger performance degradation—could similarly reduce power through increased fuel temperature and would interact with reflector temperature feedback in a comparable manner.

Table IV. Secondary salt flow rate change in the passive load-follow operation scenario.

Time (s)	0 - 30	30 - 200	200 - 2000	2000 - 2100	2100 - 2200	2200 - 2300	2300 -
$\beta_{icAi}\Gamma$ (%)	100	100 → 30	30	30 → 50	50	50 → 100	100

3.1. PLFO of Maritime MSFR without Reflector Temperature Feedback

First, PLFO was simulated without considering reflector temperature feedback. Figure 4 shows the power evolution and prompt fuel temperature feedback reactivity. Owing to the strong negative FTC, the reactor closely followed the power demand, as reflected in the fuel temperature behavior shown in Figure 5.

During power reduction, reflector temperature decreased rapidly due to reduced heating, while its recovery after power restoration was slow, consistent with conductive heat transfer behavior. The varying neutron-gamma heat source induces rather prompt temperature response and dominates the temperature change behavior in the reflector region, while the convective heat transfer between SS316 and fuel salt marginally influence on it.

Figure 4. Power profile during the PLFO without reflector feedback reactivity.

Figure 5. Temperature profile during the PLFO without reflector feedback reactivity.

3.2. PLFO of Maritime MSFR with Reflector Temperature Feedback

PLFO was then simulated including reflector temperature feedback. In contrast to the previous case, the reactor power failed to follow the demanded trajectory (Figure 6) because of positive reflector temperature feedback. The power did not recover the full 100% power level, reaching about 80% of nominal, accompanied by about 200 pcm of positive fuel temperature feedback reactivity.

Figure 7 shows the fuel and reflector temperature histories. Fuel temperature gradually decreased to approximately 2,000 s and slowly increased even after restoration of the secondary flow rate. As power rapidly dropped to about 30% of nominal, reflector temperature continued to decrease gradually due to reduced heating of 30% level. This induced gradual negative reactivity insertion, further reducing fuel temperature and power, and again consequently decreasing neutron–gamma heating in the reflector. This feedback loop would persist until the reflector temperature reaches a new equilibrium corresponding to the reduced heat source level. However, because heat removal from the reflector is governed primarily by relatively slow conductive transfer, the reflector continues to cool with decreasing power. The resulting sustained negative reactivity insertion can ultimately drive the reactor toward shutdown. Although the secondary flow rate was fully recovered after 2,300 s, heat transfer to the secondary side deteriorated because the fuel average temperature remained approximately 20 K lower than nominal. As a result, reactor power did not return to the initial level due to the insufficient positive reactivity insertion by the fuel salt.

After 2,300 s, both the power and the reflector temperature gradually increase because the reflector temperature has fallen below the steady-state level corresponding to the prevailing fission power (approximately 80% of nominal). Hence positive feedback from the reflector drives the power to approach the 100% level, which is opposite to the observation at the 30% level load-follow period. Figure 8 summarizes the reflector temperature distributions at the initial steady-state and at 4,000 s, and Figure 9 shows the region-wise reflector feedback reactivity for both PLFO cases, where the latter case exhibits lower temperatures (by ~25 K) along with enhanced insertion of negative reflector feedback reactivity.

Figure 6. Power profile during the PLFO with reflector feedback reactivity.

Figure 7. Temperature profile during the PLFO with reflector feedback reactivity.

Figure 8. Temperature distribution in the reflector after the PLFO scenarios.

Figure 9. Reflector temperature feedback reactivity profiles during the PLFO in both cases.

Figure 10 shows the asymptotic behavior of power and reflector temperature feedback reactivity to 30,000 s, assuming various RTC values and heat deposition magnitude. In the reference case (red line), the power finally converges to the initial level. However, when the RTC is doubled (blue line), the power continuously decreases because the stronger positive RTC prevents power recovery at 2,300 s, approximately below 60%. As the reflector temperature is higher than the steady-state level corresponding to the 60% power level, the power continues to decrease and ultimately leads to reactor shutdown. Furthermore, a larger fraction of heat deposition in the reflector leads to greater temperature reductions during power decrease, where it induces more negative reflector feedback reactivity like the higher RTC case.

Figure 10. Sensitivity analyses with RTC and heat source magnitude in the same PLFO scenario.

4. CONCLUSIONS

PLFO was analyzed with explicit consideration of positive temperature feedback from the moderating reflector. Although MSRs are well suited for rapid and stable PLFO due to their strong negative FTC, reflector temperature feedback no longer behaves as a purely delayed response when neutron–gamma heating is considered, complicating simple passive control strategies. Furthermore, a more positive RTC and a larger fraction of heat deposition in the reflector significantly degrade PLFO performance. Beyond the BeO reflector case, other flux-trapped MSFR configurations employing moderating reflectors such as MgO or graphite may exhibit similar challenges due to positive RTC, although the severity depends on the RTC magnitude, thermophysical properties, and the specific PLFO scenario. In cases with sufficiently high RTC values, active measures—such as direct reactivity control or dedicated reflector temperature control—may be required to prevent the reactor power from ever-decreasing and ensure reliable load-follow operation.

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